

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND LEGISLATION PERFORMANCE OF DEVOLVED SYSTEM OF GOVERNANCE, KENYA

Muchiri Albert Gakuru ¹, Dr. Muchelule Yusuf ²

^{1,2}Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology
Nairobi, Kenya

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Abstract: Corporate governance in organizations has evolved rapidly in the recent times, and its importance has been highlighted across the globe. Consequently, when adopting and implementing corporate governance, this decision may have a positive impact on decisions relating to existing investors on the one hand and potential investors on the other. County governments use the law to regulate and administer public affairs. The law is meant to address a specific social challenge or mischief. Therefore, this study determines the influence of corporate governance in the legislation performance of devolved system of governance in Kenya. There were specific objectives; To determine the role of public participation, legal framework, resource allocation and capacity building on the legislation performance devolved system of governance in Kenya. A descriptive survey research design was adopted in the three organs of government, the legislature, the executive, and the county government's judiciary with a target population of 117. Stratified random sampling, objective and simple random sampling was used to select the sample population, and the sample size was 91. Respondents with a major mandate of legislation determined using Yamane's (1967) formula. Questionnaires and self-administered interviews were used for data collection. An experimental study was conducted on 10% of the target population to determine the reliability and validity of the instrument. Close-ended questions generated quantitative data and open-ended questions yielded qualitative data. SPSS version 24 was used to analyze all quantitative data. Inferential and descriptive statistics was used to analyze qualitative data. The frequency distribution\mean, standard deviation, and percentage were included in the descriptive data. Inferential data analysis was done using Pearson correlation coefficient, regression analysis, and multiple regression analysis. The data from the questionnaire made use of both qualitative and quantitative and was coded into a Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24, which will be used to generate descriptive statistics and inferred statistics. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to establish the influence of corporate governance on the law process of devolved system of governance, Kenya. The results were presented using tables, pie charts and graphs. The study found that Corporate Governance influenced Legislation Performance significantly in devolved system of governance, Kenya. Public Participation, Legal Framework, Resource Allocation, and Capacity Building had strong positive significant relationship with Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. Corporate Governance (Public Participation, Legal Framework, Resource Allocation, and Capacity Building) explained 80.3% of Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. The results of this study will be of particular importance to the county government's assembly, especially in terms of the results and recommendations that emerge from the study. The study attempted to delve into the potential shortcomings of corporate governance relating to the law process of devolved system of governance, Kenya. The study recommends similar study to be done in other counties to ascertain the variation in Legal Performance.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Public Participation, Capacity Building, Legislation Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The leadership, governance, and structure of any corporate entity affect the entity's ability to respond to external factors, which have some bearing on its service delivery and eventual performance [1]. Perform better to a great extent and good governance principles are essential for service delivery in all institutions. It is recognized that the Asian crisis and the poor performance of the corporate sector in Africa have made the concept of governance principles a catchphrase in the development debate [2]. Corporate Governance is essentially about how the people are governed and how their affairs are handled. Law is an instrument of corporate governance. The principles of corporate governance include: discipline, accountability, fairness, independence, responsibility, transparency, and social responsibility. County governments use the law to regulate and administer public affairs. The law is meant to address a specific social challenge or mischief [3].

Corporate governance in organizations has evolved rapidly in recent times, and its importance has been highlighted across the globe. As a result, on the adoption and implementation of corporate governance, this decision can have a positive impact on decisions concerning existing investors and potential investors on the other hand [4]. In this way, the clear and important impact of corporate governance concerning the impact of these mechanisms on the performance of the law is highlighted. Many studies prove a relationship between Corporate Governance and company performance, but the results are inconsistent; Some report positive results, and others are mixed: negative and positive from company performance [3]. Various authors have divided corporate governance into various elements including transparency, accountability, participation, control of corruption, and equity [5],[1]. There are concerns that the executive branch of county government is increasingly using the law to slip into fundamental aspects of the law, including principles and policies [3]. Corporate Governance is the system by which corporations are directed, controlled, and kept in account. It is the manner in which a corporation's power is exercised in managing its total portfolio of assets and resources to increase and maintain shareholder value while meeting the needs and interests of all stakeholders [6]. Corporate Governance provides a strong foundation for the growth of economies. A good corporate governance mechanism improves the health of the corporate sector, thus enhancing national competitiveness. The corporate governance mechanism consists of a combination of economic and legal institutions that ensure the flow of external financing to the firm, align investors' interests with those of managers and other stakeholders, and guarantee returns to investors [7].

Perspectives of Corporate Governance in Kenya

The Kenyan Corporate Governance Code is divided into seven chapters that provide provisions that focus on the effective management of stakeholders as they have the potential to influence the growth of the organization and achieve long-term objectives. The Corporate Governance Code recommends proactive management of stakeholders and board relationships including identification of stakeholders, mapping areas of interaction, identification of their impact and impact, development of policies and strategies to deal with different stakeholder groups, management of expectations is included. and disclosure of conflicts of interest [8]. There is a tremendous paucity of data on Corporate Governance in Kenyans, however, in today's globally changing environment, shareholders need to maintain investment value, improve their financial performance, build a good stock market and apply corporate governance principles throughout the organization, and provides good levels of customer satisfaction [9]. The failure of corporate governance in many corporate organizations in Kenya is mainly due to poor politics, leading to poor use of shareholders' assets [4]. Although Corporate Governance policies have yielded some gains, the country is still mired in macroeconomic instability as witnessed by policy uncertainties, account deficits and high inflation rates. Despite Kenya Airways Limited winning several Corporate Governance awards over the past decade, the company has performed poorly in the form of declining share earnings every year and making losses every year [10].

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development [11] reported that state corporations in Kenya are facing performance challenges. The lack of maintained governance principles such as integrity, transparency, and accountability greatly impact the corporate performance of the state. Good corporate governance is a process of making decisions and the actual delivery of services to the people through public participation, accountability, and transparency as well as solid planning. The process must also be inclusive, foster equitability, and involve the law. Good corporate governance and quality service delivery to the general public are essential to the growth of the economy of a country due to effective legislation [12]. legislation control focuses on both the substance as well as procedures followed in making them [13]. In Kenya issues of Corporate Governance relate to accountability of stakeholders and financial malpractices. Examples Uchumi, CMC motors, and Mumias Sugar shows that due to emerging problems a lot of people were affected. Thus,

during legislation when there is limited public participation, transparency of the laws, lack of responsibility by the law makers, lack of accountability by law makers in issues to do with finances and others have led to annulment of laws and bringing laws that do not help the society. Thus, the use of Corporate Governance in the legislation process will ensure it a win-win to all stakeholders [8]. Some of the key challenges in legislation include weak capacity in law making and utilisation of evidence. This has hindered county governments in their effectiveness to make important development decisions. Most existing staff lack the requisite capacity to conduct legislative research. There is a huge capacity gap in terms of knowledge as well as the skills in relation to making laws thus, most bills are drafted by county assembly members due to lack of capacity by members of county assembly (MCAs). Further, county assemblies lack information resources centres to support evidence use. The assemblies lack county specific data for decision making as government institution such as KNBS and KIPPRA are not devolved [14]. Several studies have been conducted both globally and locally that focused on corporate governance. However, there is limited study on the influence of corporate governance on legislation process in Kenya devolved functions. This is why this study breaches this gap by examining the influence of corporate governance on the Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The general objective of this study is to examine the impact of corporate governance in the legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya.

Specific Objectives

- i. To establish the effect of Public Participation in the Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya.
- ii. To examine the influence of Capacity Building on the Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya.

Research Questions

- i. To what extent does Public Participation affect the Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya.
- ii. To what extent does Capacity Building influence the Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya.

IV. THEORETICAL REVIEW

This study will be anchored on the theories as mentioned below:

A. The Pluralist and Elitist Theory

Pluralist theory that focuses primarily on power holds that power can be in the form of several ideas such as political, religious, efficient, or driving force. This power is to be distributed to all members of the social contract and should be held more or less by no one in the institution. Pluralist theory further suggests that no one controls the social contract because everyone has an equal stake in it. The theory argues that the capabilities of the people will always exceed the powers of the executive rulers of central power. The elitist theory on the other hand stresses material power. The theory argues that those who have resources must be successful and perfect rulers, otherwise that resource would not be in their possession. Superiority among the nobility is the basis of the elite theory. One who has achieved must be of high mental capacity, and is the only one who is worthy of a position of power [17]. For the elite, citizens or "wananchi" are common due to their lack of superiority. Elitism recognizes the need for people to be governed and dictates that elites should rule because they have all the material power, they have the most, and therefore, are most likely to be lost in the event of a failed social contract. Is. If they remain in power, it is theorized that society will be in order because of the elite's desire to establish their foothold in society.

B. Participatory Theory of Development

The participatory theory of development posits that any community or society has solutions to the problems that underpin socio-economic change. It therefore, emphasizes building partnerships and using participatory and people-centred approaches to solve those problems. The principles of participatory development are all people-centred; Commitment to inclusiveness, sustainability, capacity building, self-reliance, and finally community-driven development. Participatory development is essential for at least two reasons; It empowers communities to interact with institutions of governance and thus influences public policy which provides a check to government power and secondly it increases the efficiency,

effectiveness, and sustainability of development programs. Public participatory development approach should be objective, targeted, and authentic. The approach should not be defined exclusively by managers and governors and should not be top to bottom. This approach is essentially a development around means all stakeholders of the initiative are adequately informed, engaged, and their concerns taken into account [1].

C. Stakeholders Theory

Stakeholder theory was developed by [15] and focuses on the approach to corporate responsibility relating to different categories of stakeholders. It is an evolution of agency theory in which stakeholder theory rises. Stakeholders are all persons, groups, or organizations that have an impact on the activities of the Company or are affected by the Company. It is about: owner, shareholder, investor, employee, customer, supplier, business partner, competitor, government, local government, NGO, pressure group, community, media, etc. Each of these parts affects the business of a company in one way or another [15]. Stakeholder Theory has replaced the shareholders' paradigm of Milton Friedman (1970) who held that maximizing financial results for shareholders is a company's top concern. Stakeholder theory emerges from an increasingly acute need for corporate social responsibility in the current context of the transition from an industrial society to a postmodern society. The new economy is characterized by a complex and profound change in all sectors, with major social and environmental impacts in the corporate social responsibility areas. This principle of corporate governance, based on maximizing the interests of all stakeholders, has proven to be one of the most efficient in history, not only because it drives the economic success of the company, but also because it enables people to gain competitive advantage. works for. trust and consequently a goodwill on the market.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The relationship between the dependent variable (Legislation Performance) and the independent variable (Corporate Governance) will be examined in the present study Figure I.

Figure I: Conceptual Framework

a) Public Participation

Public participation is an open, accountable and structured process where citizens or a section of people or community can interact, exchange ideas and influence decision making [16]. The Institute for Economic Affairs (2015) and the [16] viewed public participation as the process by which an organization consults with interested or affected individuals, organizations and government entities before making decisions. They see public participation as a form of two-way communication and collaborative problem solving to achieve better and more acceptable decisions. It is widely recognized that public participation contributes to better projects, better development, and collaborative governance. Research has shown that public participation is beneficial to the speed and quality of implementation of planning decisions [17]. Public participation in governance was largely perceived through elected representatives of the people and focused on access to information about government activities and engagements [18]. Currently, the focus is more than participation through elected representatives. It now focuses on citizens who have direct links with government activities and not necessarily and exclusively through elected representatives. Public participation is a constitutional right today. It is the foundation of democracy [19]. [20] citing the International Association for Public Participation, outlined a descriptive list of seven standards that would indicate that effective public participation has been made. These standards

include ensuring that the public has a direct and clear say and tangible effect on what affects them, not a symbolic opportunity; The participatory process should be inclusive, convenient, clear, information-driven, and targeted and structured so that decisions can be truly effected. Public participation is an opportunity for citizens to demand, direct and even control decision-making in matters of governance. It is a bridge between the general public and the people sitting in government offices. It is an opportunity to demand transparency and accountability in service delivery [20].

b) Capacity Building

Capacity building refers to the effort to generate knowledge, skills, and expertise to enhance analytical ability which can help in increasing productivity and livelihood. Many developed countries are using the impact assessment process to improve the quality of their policy interventions. However, only a few developing countries have systematically and consistently implemented this method of reform in their policy and legislative interventions [21]. It enhances the ability to evaluate and address policy choices and implementation methods among development options based on people's understanding and needs. Capacity building when implemented strategically can be a powerful tool to enhance the effectiveness of government to understand the needs and concerns of vulnerable members of the society or community or groups by providing them mechanisms that enable them to raise their concerns. empowers. Vulnerable group members can be empowered by providing them with relevant knowledge and information for wider benefits and better access to services. This builds trust and establishes commitment between the stakeholders and the government. The result is a community that participates in decision-making processes and available opportunities. As far as the government is concerned, it becomes sensitive to the needs of its people and can meet those needs [22]. It is now clear that while the government does not employ an impact assessment process for the proposed legislation, the resulting legislation is disorganized, unaccountable, with no clear review mechanism, and lacks invaluable input from the public [23]. The implementation mechanisms of such laws, therefore, tend to be complex and harmful to the general public. The impact assessment of the proposed legislation does not attempt to change the regulation itself. It seeks to reform the law and, possibly, provide alternative policy options that would be less costly to the public [11].

c) Legislation Process

Governance is essentially about how people are ruled and their affairs handled [18]. Law is an instrument of the government. Governments use the law to regulate and administer public affairs. The law is meant to address a specific social challenge or mischief. Furthermore, the process of law-making enforcement should be fair and people-centred and should not contradict the supreme law which is the Constitution of Kenya. The constitution confers legislative power on the representatives of the people as seen in the Kenyan Constitution and other constitutions in democratic systems globally [3]. Legislation process is a time-consuming process that has to go through several stages till it becomes law. Factors such as party bias, bureaucracy, external actors, etc. influence the process [18]. International development agencies such as the World Bank and the United Nations Development Fund (UNDP), especially in the 1970s, supported the curriculum and the relationship between good governance and development. Law is a coordination tool that promotes accountability and sustainable development [16]. Delegated law is generally a type of law made by the executive authority by the powers conferred by the primary authority to execute, enforce and administer the requirements of the primary authority. It is also known as subordinate law in administrative law. It allows the primary authority or bodies under the legislature to make laws as needed. For example, an Act of Parliament outlines a particular law that outlines the purpose for which it has been made. Thus, any legislation resulting in delegation must be in accordance with the objectives set out in the Act. In Kenya, the Statutory Instrument Act lays out thorough guidelines and a clear outline of how subsidiary legislation should be drafted, processed, examined and, approved [24].

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. A descriptive research design determines and reports the way things are [25]. A descriptive research design is used when data is collected to describe individuals, organizations, settings, or events. This study focused on the three major organs of Kenya devolved system of governance in central region (Nyeri , Murang'a, Kirinyaga and Laikipia counties) with the mandate of corporate governance on legislation; the target population of 117 are key members of county government, who have a mandate in the legislation, executive, and judiciary in the county. Yamane's (1967) formula was used to calculate the study sample size because it is simple and the population is less than 10,000. Therefore, the sample size was 91 key technical staffs with the legislative mandate in the

three arms of government (executive, legislative, and judiciary) and specific legal institutions who will be selected through simple random sampling. This study collected both primary and secondary data. Thus, questionnaires are important tools for the collection of primary data because of their many positive characteristics discussed here. A questionnaire is a research tool, which collects data on a large sample [26].

VII. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study sought to examine the impact of corporate governance in the Legislation Performance of devolved system of governance, Kenya. The sample size was 91 Respondents who work with the county government of central region. The researcher distributed 91 questionnaires to the respondents where 82 were filled and returned which account for 90.1% % of the response rate. [26] argue that a response rate of more than 50% is considered adequate while 70% is excellent.

A. Descriptive Statistics

The section attempts to establish how corporate governance influences Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance. A Likert scale was used where the responses were coded as follows: 1= Strongly Agree, 2= Agree, 3= Neutral, 4= Disagree, 5 = Strongly Disagree. The results were presented in tables and analysed and discussed. The descriptive statistics for the study variables are as follows:

1) Public Participation and Legislation Performance

The first specific objective was to establish the effect of public participation in the legislation process of devolved system of governance, Kenya. The objective attempted to answer the study question “To what extent does public participation affect the legislation process of devolved system of governance, Kenya?”. Public participation is an open, accountable and structured process where citizens or a section of people or community can interact, exchange ideas and influence decision making [16]. Table I below presents the statistics.

TABLE I: PUBLIC PARTICIPATION AND LEGISLATION PERFORMANCE

Public Participation Indicators	Mean	Stdev
The Public is sufficiently informed of opportunities and avenues available to engage and influence delegated legislation processes.	3.78	0.972
The public participation process on delegated legislation is preceded by civic education (on the delegated legislation) and therefore enriching the process.	3.44	1.130
Members of the public understand their right to public participation and hence they engage and contribute constructively to delegated legislation.	4.00	1.323
Feedback from the public during public participation influence choice of policy options around delegated legislation	3.78	0.972
In scrutinizing delegated legislation, the County Assembly satisfies itself that sufficient public participation was done before publication	3.78	1.302
Average Public Participation	3.756	1.139

From Table 4.2 above respondents generally agreed that the Public is sufficiently informed of opportunities and avenues available to engage and influence legislation processes. The mean was 3.78 and the stdev (0.972) which is less than the average Stdev (1.139) which explains that the responses did not differ a lot. The study also showed that respondents agreed that members of the public understood their right to public participation and hence they engaged and contributed constructively to legislation (mean 4.00, Stdev 1.323). Respondents agreed that feedback from the public participation influenced the choice policy options on Legislation as shown by a mean of 3.78 and Stdev of 0.972. The county assembly ensures that there was sufficient public participation before publication of the scrutinized Legislation this is supported by a mean 3.78 and Stdev 1.302. However, there was some slightly agreement on to whether public participation process on legislation was proceeded by civic education in order to enrich the process as evident by a mean of 3.44 which is below the general average. We can conclude that with a mean of 3.756 there is significant statistical evidence to suggest Public Participation influence Legislation Performance to some extent.

2) *Capacity Building and Legislation Performance*

The fourth specific objective was to examine the influence of Capacity Building on the Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. Respondents sought to answer the research question “To what extent does Capacity building influence the legislation process of devolved system of governance, Kenya?”. Responses are presented on Table II below.

TABLE II: CAPACITY BUILDING AND LEGISLATION PERFORMANCE

Capacity Building Indicators	Mean	Stdev
My institution has the technical capacity of assessing the economic, environmental, and social impact (impact assessment) of delegated legislation before it is made.	3.89	1.054
Those involved in making, scrutinizing, and operationalizing delegated legislation understand the benefits- to the institution and public – of carrying out the impact assessment.	3.78	1.202
Impact assessment on delegated legislation ensures that any proposed delegated legislation is efficient and accountable to the public.	4.22	1.394
My institution has invested resources to continuously build the capacity of those involved in making, scrutinizing, or operationalizing delegated legislation so that they can carry out an impact assessment on delegated legislation.	3.44	1.590
There is sufficient institutional support and obligation to carry out an impact assessment before delegated legislation is made.	3.22	1.394
Average Capacity Building	3.6	1.327

The study found that there was a technical capacity for impact assessment of a legislation before it is made. This is indicated by a mean of 3.89. Further, majority of the respondents agreed (mean 3.78) on carrying out of an impact assessment and its benefits. Capacity Building enhances the ability to evaluate and address policy choices and implementation methods among development options based on people's understanding and needs. Majority of the respondents (4.22) also agreed that impact assessment on legislation ensured accountability and efficiency to the public on the proposed legislation. The study however, indicated that there was no significant statistical evidence to suggest resources are invested to continuously build the capacity of those involved in carrying out impact assessment of legislation as indicated by a mean of 3.44. In addition, the study did not provide enough statistical evidence to suggest there is sufficient institutional support on carry out impact assessment on the legislation made as shown by a mean of 3.22. With a general mean of 3.6 the study provided some slightly significant statistical evidence to suggest to an extent Capacity Building influence the Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. Capacity building refers to the effort to generate knowledge, skills, and expertise to enhance analytical ability which can help in increasing productivity and livelihood [21].

3) *Legislation Performance*

The study also sought to find out about how corporate governance influenced Legislation Performance in an attempt to attain the main object of the study. To examine the influence of corporate governance on Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. Table III below shows the results from the descriptive statistics.

TABLE III: LEGISLATION PERFORMANCE

Legislation Performance Indicators	Mean	Stdev
All delegated legislations are made as required by the law.	3.33	1.000
All delegated legislations are published and tabled at the County Assembly as required by law.	3.89	1.054
Parliamentary scrutiny of the delegated legislation is robust, open, and for the common good of the public.	3.32	1.093
All delegated legislations made and approved are fully operationalized by the executive arm of government.	3.33	1.118
All delegated legislation envisioned in the parent laws are made and processed promptly	4.11	1.054
Average Legislation Performance	3.596	1.064

From Table III above, majority of the respondents agreed that legislations are published and tabled at the county assembly as required by law. This is indicated by a mean of 3.89. Further, legislation envisioned in the parent laws are promptly processed as indicated by a mean of 4.11. The study found that respondents were not sure of the operationalization of legislations that are approved this is indicated by a mean of 3.33. The study also did not show any statistical evidence to suggest the scrutiny of legislation is robust open and for the common good of the public as indicated by a mean 3.32. In addition, respondents were not convinced that legislation are made as required by the law. This is indicated by a mean of 3.33. In conclusion, with a mean of 3.596 the study provided some slightly significant evidence to suggest corporate governance to some extent significantly influences Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. [18] opines that, Governance is essentially about how people are ruled and their affairs handled. Law is an instrument of the government. Governments use the law to regulate and administer public affairs. It allows the primary authority or bodies under the legislature to make laws as needed.

B. Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics such as regression analysis and correlation analysis were used to determine the relationship between the independent variables (Public Participation, Resource Allocation, Capacity Building, Legal Framework) and the dependent variable (Legislation Performance).

i). Correlation Analysis

Pearson Correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between Corporate Governance and Legislation Performance. The findings from Table IV below show that, there is a positive and significant association between Public Participation and the Legislation Performance ($r=0.866$, p value $=0.002$). The p -value ($0.002 < 0.05$) shows the relationship is significant. Further, the magnitude of the relationship is very strong. This means that Public Participation significantly influences Legislation Performance to a great extent. In addition, there is a positive and significant association between Capacity Building and Legislation Performance ($r=0.877$, p value $=0.000$). The P -value ($0.000 < 0.05$) shows the association is significant. The association also has a strong association meaning that it significantly influences the Legislation Performance.

TABLE IV: CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS

		Legislation Performance	Public Participation	Capacity Building
Legislation Performance	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	82		
Public Participation	Pearson Correlation	.866	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002		
	N	82	82	
Capacity Building	Pearson Correlation	.877	.245	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.069	
	N	82	82	82

***Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

ii). Analysis of Variance

ANOVA was used to determine if the model was good fit for the data. As depicted on Table V below, the F calculated was 91.039 which is higher than the F critical value 2.7118. Besides, the P -value was 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05. This implies that the model was a good fit for the data hence can be used to show the impact of independent variables (Public Participation, Legal Framework, Resource Allocation, & Capacity Building) on the dependent variable (Legislation Performance).

TABLE V: ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	36.051	4	9.013	91.039	.000 ^b
1 Residual	45.820	77	.099		
Total	81.871	81			

a. Dependent Variable: Legislation Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Public Participation, Legal Framework, Resource Allocation, & Capacity Building

iii). Regression Analysis

The study assumed multiple linear relationships between the study constructs, and is expected to follow a general regression model as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon$$

The results revealed that Public Participation has a positive and significant influence on Legislation Performance ($\beta_1=0.363$, P-value= 0.048). The P-value (0.048<0.05) the significant level 0.05 hence making the relationship significant. This implies that a positive Public Participation improves Legislation Performance. Further, the results revealed that Capacity Building has a positive and significant influence on Legislation Performance ($\beta_1=0.645$, P-value= 0.000). The p-value (0.00 <0.05) makes the relationship significant. Improving Capacity Building also improves the Legislation Performance. The regression equation was thus fitted as follows:

$$Y = 0.531 + 0.363 PP + 0.645CB$$

VIII. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Corporate Governance significantly influences Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. Findings revealed that Public Participation and Capacity Building influence Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. This implies that improvement in Corporate Governance leads to improve Legislation Performance. Public Participation significantly influences Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. Public awareness on opportunities to engage and influence legislation, rights to public participation, feedback from the public participation, and sufficient public participation before publication of the scrutinized Legislation improve the legislation Performance. Finally, Capacity Building significantly influences the Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. The descriptive statistics showed that Capacity Building significantly influences Legislation Performance in devolved system of governance, Kenya. There is a technical capacity for impact assessment of a legislation before it is made. Impact assessment is done and the benefits are mad clear to the public. done and its benefits know. The impact assessment on legislation also ensures accountability and efficiency to the public on the proposed legislation. The study found Public Participation to influence Legislation Performance to a great extent. The study therefore recommends the County government should ensure there is sufficient public participation and involvement in the Legislation process. The study however did not find any suggestion that the legislation made followed limits, scope and purpose that is set out by the parent law. Thus, this study recommends legislations to follow limits and scope as set out by the parent law. Legislation should also address the principle and general framework for policy interventions as that is the task of the primary legislation. The study recommends for accountability of funds used for legislation. Further, resources should be invested to continuously build the capacity of those involved in carrying out impact assessment of legislation. There should be also sufficient institutional support on carry out impact assessment on the legislation made.

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